

Fluctuation Term in Quantum Oscillator Propagator

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In (1), the quantum oscillator propagator is obtained from the integration of the classical Lagrangian over time multiplied by a fluctuation term. In particular, a classical solution of $x(t)$ is found from the Lagrangian i.e. $x_c(t_f, t_i)$ such that $x(t_f) = x_f$ and $x(t_i) = x_i$. The Lagrangian is then expanded about $x_c(t_f, t_i) + \delta x(t_f, t_i)$. Thus, there is a term $L_c[x_c(t_f, t_i) d/dt x_c(t_f, t_i)]$ which may be integrated over time yielding a main factor of $\exp(i \int dt L_c)$ ((1)). A second factor is obtained by evaluating the $\delta x(t_f, t_i)$ term which involves some computation. In this note, we argue that the second factor, which is purely a function of time, may be obtained by inserting ((1)) into the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. Furthermore, we argue that in some cases, this approach also dictates part of the form of $\int dt L_c$. We apply this approach to a quantum oscillator and a generalized quantum oscillator.

Quantum Oscillator Approach of (1)

In (1), the propagator of the quantum oscillator $i \partial_t W = -1/2m d/dx d/dx W + .5 k x x$ W ((2)) is evaluated in the following manner. First, a classical solution for the Lagrangian is found such that $x(t_f) = x_f$ and $x(t_i) = x_i$. This solution is composed of $\sin(\omega t)$ which is a solution of the Lagrangian i.e. $T = t_f - t_i$.

$$X = x_i [\sin(\omega(t-t_f)) / \sin(\omega T)] + x_f [\sin(\omega(t-t_i)) / \sin(\omega T)] \quad ((3))$$

Inserting ((3)) into the classical Lagrangian $L_c = .5m dx/dt dx/dt + .5k x x$ and evaluating $\int dt L_c$ gives the main factor of the oscillator propagator $\exp(i \int dt L_c) = \exp(i S_c)$ i.e.

$$\exp\{-i.5m\omega [(x_i x_i + x_f x_f) \cos(\omega T) - 2x_i x_f] / \sin(\omega T) \} \quad ((4))$$

Often $x_i = x$ and $x_f = y$ and $T = t$. There is still a fluctuation factor for ((4)) which in (1) is given by a rather lengthy calculation. First, the deviation from the classical path is expressed as a Fourier series: (where $S_c = \int dt L_c$)

$$S = S_c + \delta S = S_c + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} .5 a_n^2 \{ (n^3 \cdot 14)(n^3 \cdot 14) / T - \omega \omega T \} \quad ((5))$$

The propagator is expressed as:

$$K(x, t, x_1, 0) = \exp(i S_c) Q \prod_{j=1}^{\infty} \frac{3.14 j}{\sqrt{2}} \int da_j \exp[i a_j m / 4 ((3.14 j)(3.14 j) / T - \omega \omega T)] \quad \text{where } Q \text{ is a normalization factor} \quad ((6))$$

Q is chosen to be $\sqrt{m / (6.18 i T)}$ as a kind of normalization. The integral in ((6)) is readily done, but leads to an identity which is equivalent to $\sin(3.14 x) / x$.

$$\sqrt{\frac{m\omega}{6.28 i \sin(\omega T)}} \quad ((7))$$

In this note, we argue that the fluctuation factor ((7)), which is a pure function of time, may be obtained directly from the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. Furthermore, this approach dictates part of the form of the x term (on which the Schrodinger equation operates) of ψ in $\exp(iS_c)$.

Calculation of Fluctuation Term Using the Time-Dependent Schrodinger Equation

It seems that if $\exp(iS_c)$ is known, it is simpler to insert $Q(t)\exp(iS_c)$ into the time-dependent Schrodinger equation (with x not equal y i.e x_i not equal to x_f) in order to calculate the time dependent fluctuation factor $Q(t)$.

Thus, we use: $Q(t) \exp(iS_c) = K$ ((8)) and find the result for the oscillator, by comparing purely imaginary terms:

$$dQ/dt / Q = -1/2m \frac{2A(t)}{B(t)} \quad ((9))$$

$$\text{Where } S_c = 1/B(t) [A(t) x^2 + C(t) y^2 + D(t) xy] \quad ((10))$$

The term on the RHS of ((9)) comes from the $-1/2m \frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$ Schrodinger term applied first to the x^2 exponent to bring down a linear x in the first d/dx operation. The second d/dx operation operates on x keeps the term imaginary. There is another derivative action which acts on the x^2 exponent iS_c again, but this creates a real term. The potential term is also real.

$$A(t) = -m\omega^2 \cos(\omega T) \quad \text{and } B(t) = \sin(\omega T) \quad ((11)) \quad t=T$$

$$\text{Then: } i \frac{dQ}{dt} = -1/2m \frac{(-m\omega^2 \cos(\omega T))}{\sin(\omega T)} \quad \text{so } Q = \sqrt{\frac{1}{\sin(\omega T)}} \quad ((12))$$

which is the desired result. Furthermore given the form ((10)), one sees that $B(t)$ and $A(t)$ are not independent, but for the oscillator case, $A(t) = \text{constant } dB/dt$.

This approach seems to be simpler than taking a Fourier series of a fluctuation term, integrating and using an identity together with the insertion of a "normalization" factor. The result ((12)) contains all of this.

Application of $Q(t)$ Approach to a Generalized Oscillator

In (2), a generalized operator time-dependent Schrodinger equation is given as: ($m=1, k=1$)

$$i \frac{d}{dt} (\text{partial}) W = -\frac{1}{2} (1 + \cos(2t)) \frac{d}{dx} \frac{dW}{dx} + \frac{1}{2} (1 - \cos(2t)) x^2 W - i/2 \sin(2t) [2x \frac{dW}{dx} + W] \quad ((13))$$

The factor $\exp(iS_c)$ is given as:

$$\text{Exp}\{-i [(xx-yy) \sin t \sinh t + 2xy + (xx+yy) \cos t \cosh t] / 2[\cos t \sinh t + \sin t \cosh t]\} \quad ((14))$$

This is again a quadratic Sc form, so $Q(t)\exp(iSc)$ may be inserted into the time-dependent Schrodinger equation and the pure imaginary term retained. Equation ((9)) may be used together with the purely imaginary extra term $-i/2 \sin(2t) W$ from ((13)). The result is:

$$i dQ/dt = -i/2 \sin(2t)Q + \frac{1}{2} i (1+\cos t)^2 [\sin t \sinh t - \cos t \cosh t] / 2[\cos t \sinh t + \sin t \cosh t]$$

$$dQ/dt / Q = -2 \cos t \cosh t / 2[\cos t \sinh t + \sin t \cosh t] \quad \text{or}$$

$$Q(t) = 1/\sqrt{\cos t \sinh t + \sin t \cosh t} \quad ((15))$$

This is the desired result.

Furthermore, $A(t)$ xx and $B(t)$ are again related as:

$2A(t)/B(t) + \frac{1}{2} \sin(2t)$ must yield a form of $d/dt Q / Q$ so $A(t)$ and $B(t)$ are not independent.

It may be noted, as argued in (3), that one may find the main factor of the generalized oscillator propagator $\exp(iSc)$ by postulating that $Sc = [A(t)xx + C(t)yy - D(t)xy]$ and inserting this into the time-dependent Schrodinger equation and obtaining various differential equations.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that the factor $Q(t)$ in $Q(t) \exp(iSc)$ the oscillator or generalized oscillator propagator may be found by substituting $Q(t)\exp(iSc)$, with Sc quadratic in x , into the time-dependent Schrodinger equation. We argue this is a simpler method than computing the Fourier transform of the S fluctuation, integrating and then using an identity as done in (1). We apply this method also to the generalized oscillator of (2) and note it implies certain relationships between the time coefficient of xx and its time dependent denominator.

References

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